

INTESTINAL HELMINTHES AMONG CHILDREN IN ORPHANAGES IN SOME PARTS OF KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA

Inabo, H.I and H.D. John
Department Of Microbiology, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

ABSTRACT

This study was carried out in four orphanage homes in Kaduna and Zaria, Nigeria to determine the prevalence of intestinal helminth infections among the subjects aged 0-16 years. Stool specimens and Scotch tape swabs were collected and processed according to standard parasitological techniques. Out of the ninety (90) specimens collected, 57 (63.3%) were positive for intestinal helminthes and 33(36.7%) were negative. The age group of 4-10 years had the highest prevalence of 43.8% while the children less than 1 year had the least prevalence of 5.27%. Infection with *Ascaris lumbricoides* was the highest (45.6%) while the least was observed for *Ancylostoma* spp and *Taenia* spp respectively(1.75%). Other helminthes recovered were *Schistosoma mansoni* (7.01%), *Trichuris trichiura* (22.8%), and *Vampirolepsis nana*((7.01%)). Polyparasitism was observed among the children with *Ascaris lumbricoides* + *Trichuris trichiura* (3.3%), the TRIAD- *Ascaris lumbricoides* + *Trichuris trichiura* + Hookworm (3.3%), *Trichuris trichiura* and hookworm (2.2%). Others included *Schistosoma mansoni* + *Trichuris trichiura* (1.1%), Hookworm and *Trichuris trichiura* (1.1%). Prevalence rates of intestinal helminth infections among the males were higher (54.3%) than in females (45.6%). Routine examination of stool specimens of children in orphanage homes will significantly benefit the orphans by encouraging appropriate health authorities to embark on mass chemotherapy for this vulnerable group in the Nigerian communities.

KEYWORDS: Intestinal helminthes, orphan, *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Trichuris trichiura* *Ancylostoma* spp, *Taenia* spp

INTRODUCTION

An orphan is defined as a child who had lost either or both parents and can be further categorized as maternal, paternal or double (both parents deceased) orphan. They are underprivileged children in the society and are more vulnerable to parasitic infections because of nutritional deficiencies. Intestinal helminthiasis is an important public health problem in developing countries and certain intestinal helminth infections are observed more in orphanage homes (Lindblade *et al.*, 2003).

They are also especially vulnerable to a variety of infectious diseases, including malaria, diarrhoea and respiratory disease, Intestinal parasites are more frequently encountered during childhood, since hygienic habits have not been fully developed (Ayieko, 1997).

School aged children often experience the highest incidence of geohelminth infections especially those of *Ascaris lumbricoides* and *Trichuris trichiura* (Hall *et al.*,1997).

In view of the aforementioned cases, the present study is aimed at the prevalence and distribution of intestinal helminth infections among orphans in four orphanage homes in Kaduna and Zaria, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Population

It was a cross-sectional study involving subjects enrolled from four orphanages from Kaduna and Zaria. The subjects were ninety (90) orphans aged 0-16 years. The number examined depended on those who gave their consent. The orphanages were Zaria orphanage, Zaria; Adoni orphanage, Kaduna; Jamiyar mata Arewa, City of Refuge orphanage, Kaduna, Nigeria

Ethical Consideration

Informed consent was received from the caregivers of all participating children in the four orphanages.

Use of Structured Questionnaire.

Biodata of the subjects such as age and sex and sanitation facilities such as toilet facility, source of drinking water, method of waste disposal were obtained.

Processing of the fecal specimens

The stool samples were analysed using the direct wet mount preparations and the formol-ether concentration method of Cheesbrough (2005).

Scotch Tape Swab Method

Children of four orphanages were examined with Scotch-tape technique (Cho and Kang, 1975). Faecal specimens were obtained in the morning . One drop of xylene was placed between the adhesive side of the tape and the slide, which was examined for *E.vermicularis* eggs under low power of the microscope (x4 and x10).

Statistical analysis

Significant difference between means evaluated by analysis of variance (ANOVA). Post test analysis was done using the Turkey multiple comparison tests. Values of P<0.05 were considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows that the number and percentage of positive samples *Ascaris lumbricoides* had the highest prevalence of 45.6%; others in sequential order are *Trichuris trichiura* (22.8%) ; *Enterobius vermicularis* (14.03%); *Vampirolepis nana* (7.01%); *Schistosoma mansoni* (7.01%); Hookworm and *Taenia sp.* (1.75%), The prevalence rates among the males were higher (54.7%) than the females by (45.6 %)

Table 1: Overall prevalence of intestinal helminths among orphans in four orphanage homes.

Monoparasitism	No and % positive
<i>A.lumbricoides</i>	25(45.6)
<i>E. vermicularis</i>	8(14.03)
<i>T. trichiura</i>	13(22.8)
Hookworm	1(1.75)
<i>Taenia</i>	1(1.75)
<i>S.mansoni</i>	4(7.01)
<i>Vampirolepis nana</i>	4(7.01)
Total	57(63.3)

The comparison of the prevalence of intestinal helminthes in the four orphanages is shown in Table 2. There is a significant association (p= 0.000, X² = 18.053, df = 3) between Orphanage and helminth infection using statistical level of p< 0.05. . One- way Analysis of variance to compare the means of the four orphanages showed that helminth infections in the four orphanages are not the same i.e. there is a significant difference of helminth infection in the four orphanages: p < 0.05 (p = 0.00).

Comparisons of helminth infection between the groups of the Orphanages showed that the mean difference is significant at the .05 level. The analysis showed a significant difference of helminth infection between Jamiyar mata Arewa and Adonai (p = 0.008), Jamiyar mata Arewa and Zaria (p = 0.000), and Jamiyar mata Arewa and City of Refuge Orphanages (p = 0.002).

The risk of orphans in Zaria orphanage of acquiring helminthes infection is 10 times those of Jamiyar Mata Arewa orphanage (RR = 10, 95% CI 1.56, 64.20).

The analysis indicates that orphans in Jamiyar mata Arewa orphanage are 25% more likely to acquire helminth infections when compared to those in City of Refuge orphanage, while those in City of Refuge orphanage are 75% more likely to be infected when compared to subjects in Jamiyar mata Arewa orphanage (OR 20.25, 95%CI 2.30, 178.25).

Table 2 Comparison of the prevalence of intestinal helminthes in the four orphanages

Orphanage	No Examined	No and % positive
Adoni orphanage	32	20 (62.5)
Zaria Orphanage	9	9 (100)
Jamiyar mata Arewa	10	1(10)
City of Refuge orphanage	39	27(69.2)
Total	90	57(63.3)

Polyparasitism was observed among the children(Table 3) with *Ascaris lumbricoides* + *Trichuris trichiura* (3.3%), the TRIAD- *Ascaris lumbricoides* + *Trichuris trichiura* + Hookworm (3.3%),*Trichuris trichiura* and hookworm (2.2%).Others included *Schistosoma mansoni* + *Trichuris trichiura* (1.1%),Hookworm and *Trichuris trichiura* (1.1%).

Table 3. Frequency of Polyparasitism among the orphans

Polyparasitism	No. and % positive
- <i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i> + hook worm and <i>Trichuris trichiura</i>	17 (3.3)
- <i>Trichuris</i> and hook worm	11 (2.2),
- <i>Taenia</i> + <i>T.trichiura</i>	5 (1.1)
- <i>A. lumbricoides</i> + <i>T.trichiura</i>	17 (3.3)
- <i>S.mansoni</i> and <i>T.trichiura</i>	5(1.1)
Total	55

The distribution of the helminthes by age is shown in Table 4. The age group 4-10 years had the highest prevalence (43.8%) .Children less than one year had the lowest prevalence of 5.27%.Children below ten years had higher prevalence of ascariasis, trichuriasis and hookworms than the older age groups.

The odd ratio for Age group (younger<1-10 yrs/older >11yrs) was 1.857 i.e. the younger children are 86% more likely to be infected with helminthes when compared to the older children (OR 1.86, 95% CI 0.68, 5.05). The analysis also confirms that there is no statistical association between helminth infection and age group; $p > 0.05$ ($p=0.221$, $X^2=1.495$, $df=1$)

Table 4: Age distribution of orphans with helminth infections

Age group	No. and % positive	No. and % negative
< 1	3 (5.27)	4(12.1)
1-3	10 (17.5)	7(21.1)
4-10	25 (43.8)	15(45.5)
11-15	10 (17.5)	7(21.1)
>18	9(15.78)	0(0.0)
Total	57 (3.3)	33(36. 6)

Males were more infected (54.7%) than females (45.6%).

Table 5. Comparison of water source, toilet facilities and waste disposal in the four orphanages

Orphanage	water source	toilet facility	waste disposal
Adoni orphanage	Pipe-borne	Flush system	Waste bin
Zaria Orphanage	Borehole	Pit latrine	Waste bin
Jamiyar mata Arewa	Pipe-borne	Flush system	Waste bin
City of Refuge orphanage	Pipe-borne	Flush system	Waste bin

DISCUSSION

The overall prevalence recorded (63.3%) is in conformity with other similiar studies among pre school and school aged children elsewhere in Nigeria. (Nwosu,1981; Udonsi, 1984; Obiamiwe and Nmorsi, 1991; Ukpai and Ugwu, 2003).

The prevalence of geohelminth infections among the orphans was highest with *A. lumbricoides*, followed by hookworm and lowest with *T. trichuira*. This finding agrees with those of Gilles (1996); Zulkifli (2000); Mordi and Ngwodo (2007); Nmorsi *et al.*(2009) though the subjects enrolled were not orphans but of the preschool category and in rural communities. Faecal pollution of the soil enhances the rapid spread of geohelminth infections among which ascariasis and trichuriasis are associated with children. In this study, the relatively high prevalence of geohelminthes in children living in orphanages may be attributed to poor environment and personal hygiene, shortage of potable water and indiscriminate defecation.

The statistical analysis showed a significant difference of helminth infection between Jamiyar mata Arewa and Adonai ($p = 0.008$), Jamiyar mata Arewa and Zaria ($p = 0.000$), and Jamiyar mata Arewa and City of Refuge Orphanages ($p = 0.002$). This may be due to the different water supply, method of sewage disposal and toilet facility. The analysis shows that subjects in Adonai orphanage are 7% less likely to acquire helminth infections when compared to Jamiyar mata Arewa orphanage, while orphans in Jamiyar mata orphanage are 93% less likely to acquire helminth infection when compared to those in Adonai orphanage (OR 0.67, 95CI 0.01, 0.59).

The majority of the helminth infections found in our survey were caused mainly by *A lumbricoides*. This is in agreement with earlier work done in similar studies among school aged children by Brooker *et al* (2000); Zulkifli *et al.*(2000) and Egwunyenga and Ataikiru(2005), Nmorsi *et al* (2009).

Age was an important determinant for geohelminth infection.. This has been observed in the case of infection with *Ascaris lumbricoides* by Corrales *et al* (2006). The younger children are 86% more likely to be infected with helminthes compared to the older children (OR 1.86, 95% CI 0.68, 5.05).

Possible synergistic effect of the helminthes on the immune response may be the reason for the relatively lower prevalence of polyparasitism when compared to monoparasitism. This may tend to confer some levels of protective immunity as against individuals with single infection. This observation has been documented in some parasitic co-infections. Examples include *Plasmodium* and schistosomiasis (Nmorsi *et al.* ,2009).

Co- infection of subjects with Hookworm and *Trichuris trichiura* was also observed in this study. Earlier Research work by Ezemama *et al* (2008) showed that there is exacerbation of anaemia caused by co- infection of hookworm and *Trichuris trichiura*.

Transmission of geohelminth infections is highest where children are crowded together for a long time (Harhay *et al.*, 2010). Enterobiasis was observed among the orphans living in crowded environments in the four orphanages with hygiene and exposure being important risk factors. This is in agreement with earlier works by Chang *et al.*(2009) . Inadequate personal hygiene can also increase the risk of *E. vermicularis* infection among orphans. Other risk factors, including a failure to wash hands before meals, playing on the floor and nail biting were observed to be associated with the prevalence of enterobiasis in this study.

Gravid female worms deposit their eggs near the anus on the perianal skin. Some of these eggs are detached from the perianal region and adhere to clothing, bedding and other surfaces. Infection takes place through ingestion or inhalation of infective eggs or reinfection by the migration of hatched larvae from the perianal region to the caecum. Enterobiasis is usually asymptomatic or accompanied by perianal pruritus (Remm and Remm, 2009). Some intestinal helminth infections are known to cause protein energy malnutrition and iron deficiency anemia. In Africa, children whose parents die are doubly burdened, losing not only the attention, care and advice that a parent gives, but also access to household resources such as housing and land. As a result, orphaned children are especially vulnerable and potentially at increased risk of poor health. Persistent infection with a nematode can impair physical and mental growth, poor cognitive development as well as nutritional status. (Ayieko, 1997; Hotez *et al.*,2008).

Children <6 years of age are dependent on adults to provide them with food, shelter and care.

There is increasing evidence however, that even low or moderate intensity infections significantly retard childhood growth and development (Hall, 1993; Stephenson, 1998, Muniz-Junqueira and Queiróz,2002, Hotez *et al.*, 2008).The relationship between parasitic infections and malnutrition is one of the factors emphasized in the World Development Report 1993 (World Bank, 1993).

REFERENCES

- Ayieko M.A. (1997). From Single Parents to Child-headed Households: The Case of Children Orphaned by AIDS in Kisumu and Siaya Districts. UNDP, New York.
- Brooker,S; Miguel, E.A . Moulin, S; Luoba, A.I ;Bundy,D.A.P. and Kremer.M (2000) Epidemiology of Single and Multiple species of Helminth Infections among School Children in Busia District, Kenya. *East African Journal.*77(3):157– 161
- Cheesbrough, M. (2005). District Laboratory practice in Tropical Countries. *Cambridge University Press*.
- Chang, T.K; Liao, C.W;Ying; Huang, Y.C; Chang,,C.C; Chou1,C.M; Tsay,H.C; Huang,A ; Guu,.; S.F; KaoT.C; and Fan, C.K.(2009).Prevalence of *Enterobius vermicularis* Infection among Preschool Children in Kindergartens of Taipei City, Taiwan in 2008 *Korean J Parasitol.* 47(2): 185-187.
- Cho SY, Kang SY.(1975) Significance of Scotch-tape anal swab technique in diagnosis of *Enterobius vermicularis* infection. *Korean J Parasitol.* 13: 102-114.
- Corrales, L.F, Izurieta, R.and Moe,C.L. (2006) Association between intestinal parasitic infections and type of sanitation system in rural El Salvador. *Tropical Medicine and International Health.* 11 (12) 1821–1831
- Egwyunyenga, O. A and Ataikiru, D. P(2005). Soil-transmitted helminthiasis among school age children in Ethiopia East Local Government Area, Delta State,Nigeria. *African Journal of Biotechnology.* 4 (9): 938-941,
- Ezeamama AE, McGarvey TS, Acosta PL, Ziebler S, Manaco LD, Wu H, Kurtis DJ, Mor V, Olveda RM, Friedman FJ (2008). The synergistic effect of concomitant schistosomiasis, hookworm and *Trichuris* infections on children's anaemia burden. *PLoS. Negl. Trop. Dis.* 2(6):

245. Hall, A. (1993). Intestinal parasitic worms and the growth of children. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Trop. Med. Hygiene.* 87: 241-242.

Gilles HM (1996). Soil transmitted helminth (geohelminth). *J. Parasitol.* 82(4): 527-530.

Hall, A; Orinda V; Bundy,DAP, Broun,D.(1997).Promoting child health through helminth control- a way forward? *Parasitol. Today.*13:411 - 413

Harhay, M.O., Horton,J and Olliaro.P.L. (2010) Epidemiology and control of human gastrointestinal parasites in children. *Exp. Rev. Anti. Infect. Ther.*8(2):219 - 234

Hotez, P.J; Brindley, P.J; Bethany, J.M; King, C;Pearce, E.J and Jacobson, J.(2008). Helminth Infections: the great neglected Tropical Diseases. *J. Clin. Invest.* 118 (4):1311-1321

Mordi RM and Ngwodo POA (2007). A study of blood and gastro-intestinal parasites in Edo State. *Afr. J. Biotechnol.* 6(19): 2201-2207.

Muniz-Junqueira,M.I and Queiróz,E.F.O.(2002) Relationship between protein-energy malnutrition, vitamin A, and parasitoses in children living in Brasília *Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Medicina Tropical* 35(2): 133-141

Nmorsi,O.P.G; Isaac,C . Aashikpelokhai I. S and N. C. D. Ukwandu N. C. D(2009). Geohelminthiasis among Nigerian preschool age Children. *International Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences.* 1(10). 407- 411,

Lindblade, K,A; Odhiambo,F; Rosen, D.H and DeCock, K.M (2003). Health and nutritional status of orphans <6 years old cared for by relatives in Western Kenya. *Tropical Medicine and International Health.*8 (1): 67–72

Obiamiwe, B.Aand Nmorsi, P. (1991). Human gastro-intestinal parasites in Bendel State, Nigeria. *Angrew Parasitol.* 32: 177-183.

Nwosu ABC (1981). The community ecology of soil-transmitted helminth infections of humans in a hyperendemic area of Southern Nigeria.*Annals. Trop. Med. Parasitol.* 75:175-203.

Remm,M. and Remm K.(2009). Effectiveness of Repeated Examination to Diagnose Enterobiasis in Nursery School Groups *Korean J Parasitol.* 47 (3): 235-241,

Stephenson LS, Latham MC, Kinoti SN, Kurz KM, Brigham H (1998).Improvement in physical fitness of Kenya schoolboys infected with hookworm, *Trichuris trichiura* and *Ascaris lumbricoides* following a single dose of Albendazole. *Trans. R. Soc. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 84:277-282.

Udonsi J.K (1984). *Necator americanus*: a cross-sectional study of rural community in relation to some clinical signs. *Annals of Trop. Med.Parasitol.* 78: 443-448.

Ukpai O.M and Ugwu C.D (2003). The prevalence of gastro-intestinal tract parasites in primary school children in Ikwuano Local Government Area of Abia State, Nigeria. *Nig. J. Parasitol.* 24: 129-136.

World Bank. World Development Report (1993): Investing in Health. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1993.

Zulkifli, A, Anuar A.K, Atiya,A.S. and A Yano,A.(2000) The Prevalence of Malnutrition and .Geo-helminth Infections among primary schoolchildren in rural Kelantan.*South East Asian Trop Med Public Health.* 31 (2):339-345

Received for Publication: 05/02/10

Accepted for Publication: 02/04/10

Corresponding Author

Inabo, H.I

Department Of Microbiology, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

E Mail Address: heleninabo@yahoo.co.uk